

TABLE 1—MOLAR EXCESS VOLUMES (v^E) FOR BINARY SYSTEMS OF 2,2,4-TRIMETHYLPENTANE WITH SOME ALIPHATIC ALCOHOLS AT 40°

x_1^*	Etha- nol	n-Buta- nol	Isopropa- nol	Isobuta- nol	Isoamyl alcohol
0.1	0.17	-0.02	0.23	0.01	-0.08
0.2	0.32	0.01	0.43	0.08	-0.03
0.3	0.44	0.09	0.61	0.16	0.07
0.4	0.54	0.17	0.73	0.24	0.16
0.5	0.59	0.24	0.80	0.33	0.23
0.6	0.63	0.33	0.82	0.42	0.30
0.7	0.61	0.40	0.79	0.55	0.34
0.8	0.55	0.43	0.71	0.44	0.36
0.9	0.43	0.40	0.57	0.40	0.32

* x_1 = Mole fraction of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane.

It is observed (Fig. 1) that the magnitude of v^E decreases with the increase of chain length of alkanols. Earlier, a similar dependence of excess volumes on the chain length of alkanols in carbon tetrachloride was observed¹¹ by Ramavarma and Kumaran. However, Benson *et al.*¹ while studying excess volumes of binary mixtures of n-alkanes (C_8 to C_{16}) in n-decanol, observed that excess volumes increase with the increase of chain length of n-alkane component.

Fig. 1. Plot of v^E vs x_1 for some alcohols in 2,2,4-trimethylpentane: \square —Isopropanol, \bullet —ethanol, \circ —isobutanol, \times —butanol, Δ —isoamyl alcohol.

For the systems containing ethanol or isopropanol, the excess volumes are positive over the entire mole fraction range. However, for the remaining three systems (*viz.* 2,2,4-trimethylpentane + n-butanol; + isobutanol; + isoamyl alcohol), v^E vs mole fraction curves are sigmoid with negative values over the region rich in alcohol component and the positive values in the region rich

in 2,2,4-trimethylpentane. The positive volume change may be explained in terms of the predominant intermolecular hydrogen bond stretching of associated alcohol molecules in the presence of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane. The negative values of excess volumes may be due to the predominant structural effects which arise from interstitial accommodation and changes of free volumes. The observed decrease of excess volumes with the increase of chain length of the alkanol component in the studied systems is an obvious outcome of the fact that the capability for the interstitial accommodation of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane molecules within the branched structure of the alkanol multimers increases with the increasing length of alcohol molecule.

The higher values of excess volumes in case of the solutions containing isobutanol in comparison to n-butanol solutions is due to more hindered interstitial adjustments of unlike molecules owing to the steric effect in case of the former solutions.

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Kinetics of Copper(II)-catalysed Oxidation of Formic Acid by Peroxodisulphate Ion

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EXTENSIVE studies on peroxodisulphate oxidation reactions in catalysed and uncatalysed conditions have been reported^{1,2}. A few investigations dealt with the catalytic effect of

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Ag⁺ and Cu²⁺ on the oxidation reactions⁵⁻⁸. The study of formic acid oxidation by peroxodisulphate^{6,7} has been reinvestigated⁸ to establish its probable mechanism. The present work reports the Cu²⁺-catalysed peroxodisulphate-formate reaction along with the suggested mechanism.

Experimental

Double-distilled water and AnalaR chemicals were used. Reaction kinetics were followed by estimating peroxodisulphate iodometrically. In some experiments estimations with NaOH were carried out, but the method did not give reproducible results.

Results

Uncatalysed oxidation : The uncatalysed HCOOH-S₂O₈²⁻ reaction is reported to be first order in peroxodisulphate and independent of formic acid concentration. The rate was found measurable at 60° and 0.02 M reactant concentration. The first order plots for S₂O₈²⁻ disappearance were linear and the rate constants were calculated from log (a-x) vs t plots. Fig. 1 shows plots at three

Fig. 1. First order plots : [HCOOH]₀ = [K₂S₂O₈] = 0.02(A), 0.01 (B) and 0.005 ML⁻¹(C).

different initial concentration of the reactants in stoichiometric proportion. The loss of oxidant can thus be written as

$$-\frac{d[S_2O_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k_1 [S_2O_8^{2-}] \quad (1)$$

The first order constants are practically unaffected by varying [HCOOH]₀. Thus, the rate law for the uncatalysed reaction is

$$-\frac{d[S_2O_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k_{obs} [S_2O_8^{2-}] \quad (2)$$

which is characteristic of so many peroxodisulphate oxidations.

Cu²⁺-catalysed oxidation : The oxidation is strongly catalysed by Cu²⁺ ion. The rate was

measurable at 40° and at 0.02 M reactant concentration. Fig. 2 gives the representative first order

Fig. 2. First order plots : [HCOOH]₀ = [K₂S₂O₈] = 0.02 M, and [CuSO₄]₀ = 0.0001 M. Slope = 6.67 × 10⁻³, k₁ = 15.35 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹, temp. 40°.

plot of the data. The rate constant calculated from the slope of this plot was 15.35 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹ (cf. 2.41 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹ in the absence of Cu²⁺).

Computation of the rate data in Tables 1 and 2 shows that the loss of peroxodisulphate fits the rate law given by equation (3).

$$-\frac{d[S_2O_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k_1' [S_2O_8^{2-}]^{1.5} \quad (3)$$

where k₁' is a function of the catalyst concentration.

The observed rate at different [Cu²⁺]₀ reveals that it is independent of the catalyst concentration. However, at exceedingly low [Cu²⁺]₀ (< 1 × 10⁻⁴ M) fractional power dependence is encountered. The order, when calculated between two Cu²⁺ concentrations (1 × 10⁻⁵ and 5 × 10⁻⁵ ML⁻¹), comes out to be 0.12. The rate equation may be expressed in the form :

$$-\frac{d[S_2O_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k_1 [S_2O_8^{2-}]^{1.5} [Cu^{2+}]^{0.1} \quad (4)$$

Temperature dependence : The effect of temperature on the reaction was studied in the range 30-50°. The relevant Arrhenius equation may be given by

$$k_1 = 3.63 \times 10^8 \exp\left(\frac{-18.530}{RT}\right) \text{ min}^{-1}.$$

Discussion

For the uncatalysed oxidation of formic acid by peroxodisulphate ion. The free radical mechanism of O'Flynn and House⁸ is in conformity with

TABLE 1—RATE DEPENDENCE ON REACTANT CONCENTRATIONS

[CuSO ₄] ₀ = 1 × 10 ⁻⁴ M [HCOOH] ₀ = 0.02 M				Temp. = 40° [K ₂ S ₂ O ₈] ₀ = 0.02 M		
[K ₂ S ₂ O ₈] ₀ ML ⁻¹	10 ³ Rate ML ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	10 ³ Rate [S ₂ O ₈ ²⁻] ^{1/2}	10 ³ k _t min ⁻¹	[HCOOH] ₀ ML ⁻¹	10 ³ Rate ML ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	10 ³ k _t min ⁻¹
0.010	5.90	1.48	11.81	0.01	19.51	12.63
0.015	10.47	1.62	14.28	0.02	17.23	15.35
0.020	17.23	1.88	15.35	0.03	17.71	18.48
0.030	23.49	1.58	13.98	0.04	19.36	19.96
0.040	33.20	1.58	13.31	0.05	22.33	24.95

TABLE 2—RATE DEPENDENCE ON Cu^{II} CONCENTRATION

[HCOOH] ₀ = [K ₂ S ₂ O ₈] ₀ = 0.02 M	Temp. = 40°							
10 ³ [CuSO ₄] ₀ ML ⁻¹	0.10	0.50	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	10.0	20.0
10 ³ Rate ML ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	15.64	18.15	17.23	17.69	19.16	19.38	18.07	16.83
10 ³ k _t , min ⁻¹	13.45	17.45	15.35	17.59	17.45	17.06	15.67	14.10

the observed kinetics.

It is also compatible with other peroxodisulphate oxidation mechanisms.

The Cu^{II}-catalysed oxidation reaction kinetics also exhibit the characteristics of a free radical chain process. The following few points bear importance for elucidation of the mechanism.

- (i) The rate constant for the catalysed oxidation is greater than that for the uncatalysed one, even though both the reactions obey the same rate law. This suggests that in presence of Cu^{II}, the radicals attack S₂O₈²⁻ ion at a rate faster than the radicals produced in absence of Cu^{II}.
- (ii) Evidently, the attacking radicals are readily generated from Cu^{II}-complex of formic acid, since the cupric ion is known to exist as cupric formate tetrahydrate^{9,10}.
- (iii) Cu^{II} does not, in any way, effect the rate of thermal decomposition of peroxodisulphate¹¹. Hence, Cu^{II}-catalysis of peroxodisulphate decomposition is ruled out on kinetic grounds.

A reasonable mechanism that accounts for these features and does not conflict with other evidences from peroxodisulphate oxidations could be as

The proposed steps find support from the fact that mercuric chloride reduction is observed and

inhibition is caused by oxygen as

The enhanced rate of peroxodisulphate disappearance is explained by reaction (iv) which is believed to predominate when Cu^{II} is present. Since a bimolecular reaction between peroxodisulphate ion and the catalyst is ruled out, the role of Cu^{II} perhaps becomes more significant and is different from that of Ag^I⁹⁻¹¹.

The fact that higher concentrations of Cu^{II} do not affect the rate, implies that an optimum Cu^{II} concentration is sufficient for complexation leading to radical generation by step (iv).

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